

ISic0022

I.Sicily inscription 0022

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,

inventory 3522

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]oni

2. no[---]

3. Pio η, ρ, β, ι, λ, ιss(imo) Caes(ari) pr(incipi)

4. iuv[ent] [(utis)] [---]

4. []

Apparatus

Text of

Mommsen restores

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491782

EDR 138099

EDCS 22000866

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7280 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650789>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 22

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